

Predicting financial crises with tree leaves

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Abstract

We demonstrate phylogenetic trees as useful tools for visual analysis of time series data by capturing families of cross-correlations in a single geometric object; we find the trees can also be used to predict periods of crisis as an ‘early warning’ mechanism by measuring acceleration in the change of relationships between time series. We propose a novel measure of the cohesiveness of movements between time series which presages known financial market regime-shifts when applied to a 24 global macro variable sample. Out-of-sample variable results effectively forecast the 2022 Russian ruble devaluation and produce long-short equity market returns superior to benchmark.

Keywords: Phylogenetic trees, financial regime change, inflation, volatility, exchange rates, equities, alpha

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I have nothing to disclose.

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1. Introduction

This paper introduces phylogenetic trees, a popular computational tool in biology, as a novel tool for analyzing financial market time series data. First, we show how to generate phylogenetic trees for global financial markets that convey the intricate interdependencies and movements among asset prices in an accessible visual and qualitative manner. Next, we devise a quantitative method based on these trees for pinpointing and predicting regime-shift events: periods where the nature of relationships between assets, defined for our purposes as cross-correlations in time series returns, start to change can anticipate known market downturns. The methods presented are able to capture these periods of stress using only pre-event data, suggesting a new predictive mechanism for time series analysis. This practice builds on previous works by the authors in applying volatility acceleration to the study of currency risk (Cicchetti, 2021) and phylogenetic trees to U.S. Supreme Court decision analysis (Giansiracusa, 2021). We find that the methodology performs effectively, both in its ability to predict regime-breaks and in its ability to provide researchers with visually intuitive insights concerning multi-dimensional correlation relationships. Applying the methodology to market data for the first six months of 2023, it is demonstrated to produce a 2.02% Sharpe ratio outperformance over benchmark in a Long-Short Standard and Poor's (S&P) 500 portfolio with 5 basis points of slippage and transaction costs accounted for. This proposed application triggers a sample equity portfolio to turn from long to short an index during periods where the nature of relationships in the market are changing, a proxy for periods of stress or volatility, and back to long when the phylogenetic tree unusualness measure reverts to normal.

Over the past several decades, phylogenetic trees have become a backbone of computational genetics. Typically produced from genomic distances between species to create a “tree of life” type portrait of evolutionary relationships, here we adapt phylogenetic trees to global financial markets by generating trees based on a cross-correlation distance between asset price time series. The resulting tree plots offer novel qualitative insight into market movements that can be easily interpreted. We further introduce a quantitative method for measuring the change in tree shape through time based on phylogenetic tree distances; we find that the standardized acceleration of this score (i.e., the moving-average standard deviation of its second derivative) spikes just prior to market-disrupting events. This can be used to study regime shifts retroactively, as well as to anticipate their occurrence in real time.

Our methodology, described in detail in Section 3, may be summarized as follows: unusualness of the rate of change in the shape of a tree from one period to the next is the independent variable used in predictive analysis of financial markets over various samples. We first demonstrate, using synthetic mathematical time series with artificially constructed ‘break’ points, the regime-change detection utility of the “tree distance series” (D), which measures the evolution of the tree over time. The mathematical framework is tested over various time-series break horizons and demonstrates the ability of phylogenetic tree distance series to detect periods of regime change. This method is then applied to financial markets, testing whether spikes in the unusualness of the moving-average standard deviation of D ’s second derivative, or acceleration in the change of the tree shape, coincide with three known global macro regime-shift events. We then test for spikes in tree distance series unusualness using only pre-break data across the three

separate instances of known regime-breaks to evaluate the tool as an effective ‘early warning’ system for market distress. Finally, the tree distance series change unit is tested for statistical significance against the total time-series sample of each regime-change event; a verified lagged relationship acts as a robustness test as it shows the measurement of tree shape change to be significant to existing statistical methods of capturing total system movement. The three known instances are the 2013 Taper Tantrum, the 2020 COVID-19 Pandemic, and the 2021 Inflation Scare. An out-of-sample test on Russian ruble prices around the 2022 invasion of the Ukraine is conducted using an alternative basket of currency variables, followed by an additional out-of-sample proposed implementation framework through a US long-short equity portfolio model.

We find the macro tree (MT) visual analysis framework offers an important new tool to describe the drivers of risk either at the single-asset or portfolio level. There are a variety of widely recognized macro factors that may potentially describe global market co-movements at any given time, though the study of market movements as described by these factors in conjunction with one another is widely discussed via statistical sensitivity of each factor within a single system. Tools that provide ‘early-warning’ indicators that financial markets have shifted to a new level of sensitivity across factors, however, are of interest given the “devastating economic, social and political consequences” involved with such changes (Fu, Zhou, Liu & Wu, 2020). Regime shifts, where the driving forces of market price co-movements change, are closely related to defining when a country or market is entering a crisis period. The application of this paper’s findings with regards to predicting financial crises is intentional in addressing a gap in the literature in volatility acceleration studies as they relate to global markets, as well as in providing investors and

policymakers new tools to promote international investment with reduced risk. For demonstrative purposes the data-sample refers to currency markets and a limited number of precious metals and oil prices, as well as inflation and world equity baskets. The proposed application framework demonstrates the effectiveness of the methodology in providing early warnings for asset market disruption, potentially generating significant economic value and mitigating a wide variety of risks without succumbing to sampling issues related to traditional shock indicators.

This paper is organized as follows: a discussion of phylogenetic trees precedes a literature review of regime-change importance and commonly used identification mechanisms (Section 2). Section 3 describes the phylogenetic tree construction methodology, the use of tree distance as a measurement unit, mathematical proof-of-concept work, and sensitivity testing to gauge whether the tree-breaks are correctly identifying known regime-change periods followed by predictive capability, robustness testing and a proposed implementation framework. This paper uses a combination of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Models to compare the phylogenetic tree distance series to the return of financial markets over time. This paper's phylogenetic tree construction methodology is deployed in RTM and is built on standard freely available phylogenetic libraries.

This paper uses a sample of daily data with a representative basket of global macro factors including developed market (DM) and emerging market (EM) currencies that allow for spot settlement of transactions, global equity indices, commodity prices and U.S. inflation indicators. A full description of the data is available in Section 4. Both visual analysis and empirical results are demonstrated in Section 5, and implications of both are detailed in Section 6.

2. Literature Review

A review of phylogenetic trees is followed by a discussion on regime-change detection. The phylogenetic tree review includes some brief mathematical background and terminology that will be relied on later in the paper.

2.1 Phylogenetic trees

Phylogenetic trees emerged in the 20th century as a ubiquitous computational tool in genomic sciences to capture the evolutionary relationships between species or other biological entities. Charles Darwin had earlier popularized the idea of a “tree of life” in his seminal book *The Origin of Species*, but he faced the daunting task of drawing trees by hand, so his works were not as quantitatively detailed as modern phylogenetic trees. In the past several decades science has been gifted both a wealth of detailed genomic data as well as the powerful computational resources needed to process it, and in this time phylogenetic tree analysis has flourished. Those interested in learning about the biological origins and applications of phylogenetic trees are encouraged to consult the popular textbook *Inferring Phylogenies* (Felsenstein, 2003), but such reading is not at all necessary for the present paper. Indeed, all we need is the abstract notion of a phylogenetic tree and a quick description of the algorithms available for computing them from data.

First, recall that a *graph* is a mathematical object consisting of vertices and edges connecting certain pairs of vertices. A *path* in a graph is a sequence of distinct edges in the graph such that each pair of adjacent edges in the sequence meets along a common vertex. This is usually framed as a path between a pair of vertices, in which case the path simply describes a way of walking along the graph between the two vertices. A graph is called a *tree* if there is a unique path

connecting any pair of vertices. This is equivalent to the graph being *connected* (there is a path connecting any pair of vertices) and *acyclic* (there is no path from a vertex to itself). These standard definitions are intended to convey mathematical precision, but ultimately a tree is simply a network that branches out without the branches ever merging back together. Trees have two types of vertices: *interior* vertices (where branching occurs) and *leaves* (the endpoints of branches). To use more precise language, the *degree* of a vertex is the number of edges attached to it, and the leaves are the degree 1 vertices in a tree whereas the interior vertices are the vertices with degree greater than 1.

A *phylogenetic tree* is a tree in which all the edges have been assigned a nonnegative number that we usually think of as the *length* of the edge. In the biological setting the edge lengths represent an evolutionary distance, such as the time it took for one species to split into multiple distinct species, but a direct interpretation of this sort is not necessary when working with phylogenetic trees. The fact that edges all have lengths and that there is a unique path between any pair of vertices means it makes sense to talk about the *distance* between any two vertices in a phylogenetic tree. The most important instance of this is the distance between two leaves of the tree; in biology this corresponds to a measure of the genomic distance between two species, whereas in this paper it will capture a market behavior distance between two financial product time series, as will be explained shortly.

One of the central computational problems in phylogenetics is *tree estimation*, which means the following: given m entities and some form of pairwise distances between them, construct a phylogenetic tree on m leaves such that the tree distances between the pairs of leaves

are as close as possible to the original pairwise distances. The “as close as possible” is open to various interpretations, but the most prevalent one is to minimize the sum of the squares of the differences between the two kinds of distances; this is referred to as the ordinary least squares (OLS) tree determined by the input data. While tree estimation originated in genetics and derives much of its terminology from that setting, it is important to note that there is nothing inherently biological about this process: it is simply a way of creating the tree that best approximates, via leaf-to-leaf path lengths, the distances between m entities.

In biology one often needs to perform tree estimation for large numbers of leaves, which even with today’s computational resources is too difficult to achieve using least squares optimization methods. For a given tree type the problem is linear, but the number of tree types suffers an unavoidable combinatorial explosion as the number of leaves increases. Accordingly, practitioners have had to develop various heuristic approaches that find good trees in a reasonable amount of time rather than holding out hope for OLS trees. In 2014, *Nature* published a list of the top 100 most-cited scientific papers of all time (Van Noorden, Maher & Nuzzo, 2014), and coming in at #20 on the list was a paper from 1987 introducing a particular tree estimation algorithm (Saitou & Nei, 1987). In the present paper we generally use a small enough number of leaves that we can always compute the actual OLS tree so we do not make use of these heuristic algorithms, and though the issue of computational power is out of scope for this paper there is a vast literature on speeding up tree estimation by looking beyond OLS.

Despite the ubiquity of trees in a variety of settings and the generality of the tree estimation process, it is somewhat surprising that tree estimation has not been applied more broadly. We are

primarily familiar with its usage outside of biology from the second author's work on using trees to study the U.S. Supreme Court (Giansiracusa, 2021 & 2022). There, the voting disagreement rates of the justices are used as the pairwise distances and the corresponding 9-leaf OLS trees are explored. The interpretation and applications of trees depends very much on the particulars of the setting, so aside from the general use of OLS tree estimation, there is almost no overlap between those two papers and the present one.

2.2 Regime Change Definition

The effort to study regime-shifts is reflective of a known front-loaded drawdown effect following financial market shocks where the largest losses occur in the immediate aftermath of a downside market trigger. This is derivative of the leverage effect (Black, 1976). Many studies evaluate early warning systems for financial crises in various markets, be they debt, currency, commodity, or stock market shocks as concisely listed by Fu et al., 2020 (Section 1 para 2). This paper seeks to provide a unified framework with which to detect early warnings in a variety of ecosystems, including for demonstrative purposes global markets involving all four aforementioned variable classes. This paper's acceleration methodology builds on previous work in applying acceleration frameworks to future quarterly return estimations (He & Narayanamoorthy, 2019), though these methods have largely been confined to stock market analysis. Related to the leverage effect, where acceleration signals may be seen as a precursor to market negative events, the use of volatility acceleration has been previously proposed in currency options pricing theory (Baaquie & Cao, 2014) where in periods of crisis "[options] traders have less confidence in the market," (Baaquie & Cao, 2014, p. 348) though this research has yet to be extended to practical applications in other

fields. There are examples of applying long-term economic growth acceleration as it relates to development (Hausmann, Pritchett, & Rodrik, 2005), but to the best of our knowledge this is the first attempt to apply acceleration frameworks to broader volatility analysis. This follows previous work in the space by the first author on currency volatility acceleration (Cicchetti, 2021), but its application in the methodology that follows is unique to this paper.

The concept of distance as a measure to model financial market states has previously been investigated under a Mahalanobis distance framework (Procacci & Aste, 2019), though focused exclusively on US stock indices. Tree methods themselves have previously been employed in the modeling of financial phenomena such as commodity crisis forecasting (Zhang & Hamori, 2020) and lending risks (Malekipirbazari & Aksakalli, 2015), though such studies follow the popular random forest framework in machine learning (Liaw & Wiener, 2002) and not phylogenetic-distance comparison between cross-correlation time series trees. This paper provides an expansion of the research in applying regime-shift studies to broader global macro instruments as well as a novel phylogenetic tree-distance-based conceptual framework.

This paper's methodology has the added benefit of expanding on research that time-dummy variables are significant in specifying cross-market correlation models (Büyüksahin & Robe, 2014) and time-varying analysis states (Wen, Wei, & Huang, 2012) yet separates itself from such efforts that rely on arbitrary crisis-state definitions around large global events such as the 1997 East Asian Crises (Forbes & Rigobon, 2002) or the 2008-9 global financial crisis which will "generally...cause asset prices to plunge across markets and will create speculative runs and capital flight, leading to considerable market instability" (Wen et al., 2012, p. 1435). Global macro

volatility is sensitive to global systemic risk, as evidenced by the large known impact of the global financial crisis and the well-analyzed commodity-to-equity market spillover effects of the Lehman crisis where “cross-market correlations increase in globally bad economic times,” (Büyüksahin & Robe, 2014, p. 64). Alternatively relying on a nominal volatility threshold, or a quantile-of-return extremity threshold-based methodology (Bae, Karolyi, & Stulz, 2003, p. 726) to discern states of volatility may create false-positives should currency markets remain in elevated-volatility environments. The use of historically based crisis sampling has come under criticism previously in the study of market fragility, where the literature on equity market contagion suggests “no evidence for a clear relationship between excess co-movement and commonly used crisis samples” (Mierau & Mink, 2013, para. 4).

This work combines various techniques that have been applied to financial market time series analysis with degrees of complexity in cross-correlation analysis, including PCA (Alshammri & Pan, 2021, Chang, Guo & Yao, 2018, Fu et al., 2020, and Rigobon, 2016) and volatility acceleration (Cicchetti, 2021); the latter is designed to complement existing techniques of risk management and forecasting power that leverage forms of volatility analysis, including Bollerslev, Tauchen & Zhou, 2009, and Atilgan, Bali & Demirtas, 2015. The result is a novel, unified approach to regime shift detection that is applicable to a wide range of markets.

3. Methodology

This section first details phylogenetic tree construction in the context of time series data followed by measurement of change in the trees over time via ‘distance.’ The use of distance as a means to detect regime changes in time series data is detailed in Section 3.3. A synthetic mathematical time

series framework is put forward to demonstrate the validity of using distance in identifying regime-change breaks before testing with financial market data. This is followed by verification of the explanatory power of the distance measures onto collective financial asset time series, along with standard statistical robustness tests. Finally, a proposed implementation trading framework is proposed.

3.1 Phylogenetic Tree Estimation for Time Series Data

Suppose we are given a set of m time series, $\mathbf{X}^1, \mathbf{X}^2, \dots, \mathbf{X}^m$. We can consider the *cross-correlation based distance* (CCD) between any pair i and j of the set:

$$\text{CCD}(\mathbf{X}^i, \mathbf{X}^j) = \sqrt{\frac{1 - \rho_{i,j}^2(0)}{\sum_{k=1}^{\max} \rho_{i,j}^2(k)}} \quad (1)$$

where $\rho_{i,j}^2(k)$ is the cross-correlation between \mathbf{X}^i and \mathbf{X}^j with lag k (Liao, 2005, Section 2.2.8). Throughout this paper, we shall refer to the OLS tree determined by these pairwise CCD distances simply as the “tree determined by the times series $\mathbf{X}^1, \dots, \mathbf{X}^m$ ” (leaving the choice of cross-correlation based distance and OLS estimation implicit). Other time-series distance measures are potentially valid, but we believe cross-correlation is the most reasonable for financial data; further optimization around choice of measure is out of scope for this paper. To add additional flexibility, rather than using time series data for the full span of time stamps available, we will usually choose a start time and a stop time and consider the tree determined by the corresponding truncations of the time series; when the time series are clear from context, we will refer to this simply as the tree between start and stop times.

3.2 Tree Growth over Time

If we do not truncate our collection of time series, then the phylogenetic tree produced from their cross-correlation distances will capture their overall relationships across the entire time span of the time series. It would be useful to have something more akin to a snapshot of the tree at each moment in time, but this is not possible since cross-correlations are only defined across ranges of time, not at individual time stamps. To get past this obstacle, we introduce here a method for quantifying the change in shape of the tree throughout the range of time stamps in the time series underlying the tree.

Continuing the notation from the preceding subsection, consider our collection of m times series X^1, \dots, X^m that all start at time $t=1$ and end at time $t=n$. For each time stamp $t=s$ between these values where $1 < s < n$, let $T1$ denote the tree from $t=1$ to $t=s$ and let $T2$ denote the tree from $t=s+1$ to $t=n$. We then compute the tree distance between $T1$ and $T2$ (defined in the following paragraph). This yields a new time series of tree distances that, roughly speaking, records how dissimilar the “before s ” tree is from the “after s ” tree.¹ We call this the “tree distance series,” denoted as D . This is the same distance D measure as mentioned in Section 1.

There are multiple notions of tree distance in the phylogenetics literature. Some only incorporate the topology of the tree, but we prefer one that also incorporates the lengths of the edges in the tree. The most natural one that does so is the “branch score” (Kuhner & Felsenstein, 1994) where for each partition of the leaves of a tree T into disjoint sets, let b_P denote the length

¹ Some distance data points at beginning and end of the new time series are lost due to the computation of cross-correlation.

of the edge in T inducing this partition, if such an edge exists, and let it equal 0 otherwise. Given trees T and T' on the same set of leaves, the branch score is the sum of squared differences $(b_P - b_{P'})^2$ over all bipartitions of the leaves. Throughout this paper, whenever we compute a tree distance series, we rely on this branch score for the notion of tree distance.

3.3 Distance and Regime Change

Tree distance is posited as a useful measure to tell when the nature of relationship in a network is changing. The interrelation of correlations in a set of variables, traditionally viewed via a two-dimensional matrix, is placed in a network context via the phylogenetic tree methodology. The structural relationships, as measured via networked tree-branch proximity between these variables, is presumed to change over time to some degree in a dynamic environment; the basic structure of the tree, *ceteris paribus*, is not expected to change dramatically. Structural shifts, however, are precisely what this methodology is intended to detect and ultimately predict. If there is a structural shift that changes the nature of relationships within the network, this is expected to be reflected in an unusually large change in distance. Measuring how the tree shape changes over time, and how unusual these changes are relative to history, constitutes the basis of this detection methodology. Distance unusualness (DU) as a time series is defined as a rolling average of volatility in tree distance over the total sample's volatility:

$$\mu_t = \frac{\sum_{i=t-9}^t D_i}{10} \quad (2)$$

$$\mu_N = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N D_i}{N} \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_t = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=t-9}^t (D_i - \mu_t)^2}{10}} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_N = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (D_i - \mu_N)^2}{N}} \quad (5)$$

$$DU_t = \frac{\sigma_t}{\sigma_N} \quad (6)$$

An unusualness reading above 1 would imply that the previous ten periods of distance exhibited greater volatility than that of the total sample of volatility in phylogenetic tree structure. For a controlled set of data, an extremity threshold of 1 can be reasonably assumed as significantly unusual distance behavior, but for a more volatile set of data where relationships are constantly in flux more sensitivity in unusualness detection would be prudent.

Significant changes in the shape of the tree measured this way reflect a change in the structure of the dataset. This implies that the nature of cross-variable correlations itself has shifted along some underlying change in causal structure. In keeping with the logic of the leverage effect, in a financial market context although such changes could be positive for asset markets they are assumed to predominately be negative. Changes in market structure, especially disruptive ones that bring sudden shifts in correlations, are expected to coincide with volatility. Before applying the framework to financial market data, the basic tenets of this methodology are tested using stable synthetic data. These tests are described in the following section.

In applying the framework to financial markets, acceleration in the unusualness of distance comprises the bulk of the paper's analytical work. The complexity of financial markets means that trees are continually expected to be changing shape to some degree, and as such an additional level of granularity is added to the analysis of the unusualness of tree shape change. This 'distance acceleration unusualness' methodology is developed to detect known financial market 'regime-

change' events, where singly important and acknowledged phenomena lead to periods of sustained negative returns. The methodology is then tested predictively with known regime-change periods by only including pre-event data. This is to test whether or not financial markets are able to 'anticipate' regime-changes in a way that is detectable via the unusualness with which market variables cross-correlate to one another.

As per Cicchetti (2021), a simple forward-looking distance acceleration function (DA) is added, the result of the difference of the previous-to-current period phylogenetic tree distance series D change versus that of the previous periods:

$$DA_t = \frac{\frac{D_t - D_{t-1}}{D_{t-1}} - \frac{D_{t-1} - D_{t-2}}{D_{t-2}}}{\frac{D_{t-1} - D_{t-2}}{D_{t-2}}} \quad (7)$$

A ten-period² standard deviation (σ_t) of the acceleration function weighted by the full-sample (σ_N) standard deviation comprises the 'unusualness' (Ξ) signal:

$$\mu_t = \frac{\sum_{i=t-9}^t DA_i}{10} \quad (8)$$

$$\mu_N = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N DA_i}{N} \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma_t = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=t-9}^t (DA_i - \mu_t)^2}{10}} \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_N = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (DA_i - \mu_N)^2}{N}} \quad (11)$$

$$\Xi_t = \frac{\sigma_t}{\sigma_N} \quad (12)$$

² The ten-period length was chosen arbitrarily, and though optimization testing is out of scope for this paper it is warranted in future research.

For the purposes of identifying regime change within known data samples, acceleration signals are unbounded; for forward-looking predictive applications, negative-acceleration events are screened out. Acceleration signals in equation (7) are only observed in cases where the first derivative of volatility is positively signed in the numerator where $D_t - D_{t-1} > 0$. While the acceleration signals' basic equation disallows for downward acceleration 'false-positives,' in practice this is not regularly observed; this is in line with established market observations around the behavior of volatility as a predominately price-negative event (Black, 1976; Candelon & Straetmans, 2006). \mathcal{E} peaks within samples are expected to identify regime-change according to an extremity constant. This extremity constant may vary according to use-case and/or optimization testing, though for our purposes may be posited as a market-standard one-sigma ($\mathcal{E} > 1.68$) level. Alternatively, as per the more simple distance unusualness framework, a signal above 1 would imply that the moving-window in the time series is more volatile than the full-sample. This would lower the barrier for an extremity signal but, in lieu of further optimization testing, may provoke 'false positive' signals during periods of extended market volatility. Both extremity constants are tested in out-of-sample applications as described in Section 3.6.

3.4 Harmony versus Discord Proof of Concept

Two data generation models are developed to test the tree distance methodology's utility in detecting regime-shift events using purely synthetic data and arbitrarily defined time series: "*Harmony*" and "*Discord*." This proof-of-concept framework tests whether tree distances indeed serve as functional units of measurement in detecting regime-change under theoretical conditions. Under the *Harmony* parameters, a very simple complete (i.e. completely known) single-variable

system where a single “*Theme*” time series is known to causally explain ten other “*Chord*,” or “*C^x*” time series is produced using EXCEL™’s random number code;

$$\mathbf{Theme}_t^{Harmony} = \mathbf{Rand}_t \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_t^x = (\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{1}) + \left(\frac{\mathbf{1}}{\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{1}} * \mathbf{Theme}_t \right) ; \mathbf{for} \ \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{1}, \mathbf{2}, \dots \mathbf{10} \quad (14)$$

The EXCEL™ “RANDBETWEEN(1,200)” function, or “*Rand*,” generates a random integer between 1 and 200 for each time “*t*” where $x = 1, 2, \dots, 10$. Under these conditions, a randomly generated *Theme* series will fully explain all deviations in the overall model, as the *Chord* time series differences are all derived from the one *Theme*. In other words, every *Chord* will exhibit a positive correlation to *Theme* in steadily declining extremity as x increases.

In the *Discord* formulation, it is arranged that at one ‘break’ point the *Chord* time series will take on new characteristics that constitute a new “regime”:

$$\mathbf{Theme}_t^{Discord} = \mathbf{Rand}_t \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_t^x = \mathbf{Rand}_t ; \mathbf{for} \ \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{1}, \mathbf{5}, \mathbf{8} \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_t^x = (\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{1}) + \left(\frac{\mathbf{1}}{\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{1}} * \mathbf{C}_t^1 \right) ; \mathbf{for} \ \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{2}, \mathbf{3} \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_t^x = \mathbf{C}_{t-1}^x + \mathbf{1} ; \mathbf{for} \ \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{4} \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_t^x = \frac{\mathbf{C}_t^5}{\mathbf{7}} + \mathbf{C}_{t-1}^x ; \mathbf{for} \ \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{6} \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_t^x = (\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{1}) + \left(\frac{\mathbf{1}}{\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{1}} * \mathbf{C}_t^8 \right) ; \mathbf{for} \ \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{9}, \mathbf{10} \quad (20)$$

At some break point b , for $t < b$ the *Chord* time series will follow *Harmony* under equations (13-14) but for all $t \geq b$ they will follow the new regime *Discord* under equations (15-20). In this new

regime, *Theme* no longer explains any other variable, *Chords* 2 and 3 are following a random *Chord* 1, *Chord* 6 follows a random *Chord* 5 (as do 9 & 10 with a random *Chord* 8), and *Chord* 4 now iterates by one. As proof of concept that changes in tree distances are useful in identifying changes in time series regimes, the distance unusualness (*DU*) methodology is employed, as defined in the previous section in equations (2-6), and applied to a set of various trials under this *Discord* framework. The *DU* signal is monitored over the time-series for indications of what constitutes a break corresponding to the known shift from Harmony to Discord. As the change is mechanically introduced, a regime-change is expected with no prior indication of unusual distance behaviour. This test is run multiple times using different randomly generated numbers for each relevant variable over a 40-period series with Discord breaks; ten trials are tested with breaks at $b=21$ and then ten trials are tested again with Discord breaks at $b=35$. Ten tests are run with no Discord break (i.e. a full Harmony series) for comparison. *DU* readings for Harmony specifications are not expected to show any readings above 1 as the stable pattern of the system would not imply any tree distance shift from one period to another being greater than the overall sample's volatility. *DU* results are expected to show spikes in line with the known Discord breaks for each testing condition, thus demonstrating the basic utility of tree distances in monitoring changes in time series cross-correlations. The results of our experiments with this synthetic Harmony and Discord data are presented in Section 5.

3.5 Robustness Testing

Standard statistical robustness tests are applied to financial market-based findings, along with testing for significance between the phylogenetic tree-distance measures and the collective sample

variable time series. Time series are checked for stationarity under Dickey-Fuller (DF) testing. A full-time series PCA for each of the three sample periods is generated using level time series data:

Principal components is a non-parametric methodology that finds a linear combination of the variables of interest that maximizes the explanatory power. In any data there are as many principal components as variables. (Rigobon, 2016, Section 4.1.2)

“PCA” for the purposes of this paper refers exclusively to the statistical first component time series, or the derived maximum-explanatory power component.

Returns of the PCA series are then evaluated against the second difference of tree distance, DA , under ARDL specifications. DA is tested against PCA for explanatory power of tree distances on time series rather than $\bar{\varepsilon}$ (which represents the smoothed unusualness of DA for use in identifying breaks in said time series). Both PCA and ‘distance acceleration’ DA series include pre-and-post event data. This paper uses an ARDL framework due to the inability to confirm tree distance as having first-order integration, and due to consideration of the known variation in stationarity of levels for various currency markets (see Table 3). An optimal-lag ARDL Model is implemented in STATATM, where lagged PCA time series returns ($rPCA$) are described by lagged tree distance acceleration. Dependent variable lags (p) for (j) number of exogenous variables, and variable lags (q) are selected via an Akaike information criterion (AIC). A constant (γ) and short run dynamic coefficients of the model’s adjustments to long-run equilibrium (λ_j and β_j) are tested for significance where (ε) is a vector of error terms:

$$rPCA_t = \gamma + \sum_{j=1}^p \lambda_j rPCA_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^q \beta_j DA_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad (21)$$

Residual autocorrelation is tested for under Breusch-Godfrey (1978) parameters, as is heteroscedasticity under a White test implemented in STATA™. Where crisis-returns are found to be significant, a model is implemented with Huber/White/sandwich (White, 1980) robust standard errors. Results that pass the robustness tests demonstrate that phylogenetic tree distance acceleration has statistically significant explanatory power on returns of a collective basket of financial asset time series.

3.6 Proposed Implementation Framework

Using data from December 30th 2022 to June 20th 2023, a long-short S&P 500 portfolio using a mock starting amount of \$100,000.00 is implemented in STATA™. The portfolio (P) is 100% long the S&P 500 (SPX) except during Ξ signal periods where it turns 100% short, flipping back to long once the signal subsides. Five basis points, or 0.05%, are removed from the total portfolio value during both long-to-short and short-to-long flips for both theoretical transaction cost (TC) and slippage cost (SC) each time the portfolio ‘transacts.’

$$\text{If } \Xi_{t-1} > \Pi \text{ Then } P_t = \frac{P_t * (1-TC) * \frac{SPX_t}{SPX_{t-1}}}{1+SC} \text{ Else } P_t = P_{t-1} * \frac{SPX_t}{SPX_{t-1}} ; \text{ for } \Xi_t \leq \Pi \quad (22)$$

$$\text{If } \Xi_{t-1} \leq \Pi \text{ Then } P_t = \frac{P_t * (1-TC) * \frac{SPX_{t-1}}{SPX_t}}{1+SC} \text{ Else } P_t = P_{t-1} * \frac{SPX_{t-1}}{SPX_t} ; \text{ for } \Xi_{t-1} > \Pi \quad (23)$$

For testing purposes, two Ξ extremity thresholds (Π) are modeled: 1.00 and 1.68. US Generic Government 10-Year Yield (US10Y) returns are used as a risk-free rate measure when calculating Sharpe ratio performance of the S&P 500, portfolios and comparison Exchange Traded Fund

(ETF) benchmarks. A limited basket of ETFs has been selected to represent a variety of popular and investor-accessible equity market strategies.

4. Data

The chosen sample group of variables listed in Table 1 offers a representative testing ground for macro regime-change analysis, including only liquid (i.e., spot deliverable) currencies from Asia-Pacific, Europe, Africa, and the Americas. All time series returns are daily and denominated in U.S. dollar. The US dollar index is included in the currency basket in order to screen for exogenous effects. U.S. “rates” are the primary inflation-sensitivity variable in the basket as the three chosen regime-shift events are observable via S&P500 dislocations. Global equity returns are proxied via the relevant Morgan Stanley Capital International (MSCI) country indices for standardization purposes. Descriptive statistics for time series logarithmic returns over the full dataset history are listed in Table 2. Three known ‘regime-shift’ events, including two instances of market reactions to U.S. monetary policy concerns, are chosen from within the full sample January 2nd, 2012 to December 13th, 2021 window: the May 22nd 2013 ‘Taper Tantrum’ event (Taper), the COVID-19 global pandemic (COVID) and the November 24th 2021 ‘inflation shock’ event (CPI).

A test on a set of out-of-sample variables is run for historical Russian ruble spot data; this test uses an alternative basket of 14 currencies, listed here according to Short ID (Table 1): DXY, AUD, ZAR, TRY, MXN, NZD, CAD, EUR, GBP, NOK, SEK, CHF, PLN, and RUB. The daily sample data is taken from January 3rd, 2022 to April 8th, 2022 to cover the Russian Federation’s invasion of the Ukraine and the associated local currency dislocations. \mathcal{E} testing using only pre-event data is run under the parameters of Section 3.4. All data is sourced from Bloomberg, L.P.

5. Empirical Results

The Harmony vs. Discord testing shows the tree-distance unusualness methodology accurately identifies historically-known regime-changes in the relevant time series. In the market-data regime-shift predictive experiments, in each case using only pre-event data the tree unusualness measure shows a dramatic uptick in extremity. This differs from the Discord proof-of-concept outcomes where tree distance ‘jumps’ coincide directly with known hard-coded breaks; with the market data the \bar{E} measure reflects jumps in anticipation of the historical regime-shifts. These results show robustness in all but one case where multiple regime-shifts in a single sample can be seen to disrupt the methodology. The methodology is also shown to be able to forecast the Russian ruble devaluation two days in advance of the currency downturn associated with the February 2022 invasion of the Ukraine. The proposed implementation framework yields profitable results in a long-short S&P500 portfolio on a notional and Sharpe ratio basis.

5.1 Harmony versus Discord Results

The ‘harmonic’ system can be illustrated in Figure 1, where a phylogenetic tree is produced from the Harmony methodology (Section 3.4) in which ten Chord (C1, C2,...,C10) time series are translated and rescaled versions of a single randomly generated Theme time series. As resultant changes in the Harmony system are derived from changes in the single Theme time series, the phylogenetic tree shows all Chords emanating from the single Theme branch (or ‘trunk’) in a pattern evocative of a fractal framework. The geometric shape of the tree may indeed change based on various specifications, but within the Harmony structure the shape is consistent across a variety of random Theme variable iterations.

Applying Discord has a notable effect on the shape of the tree: visual analysis for a time series break at $t=21$ shows the first half (under Harmony specifications) as being consistent with previously observed fractal shapes along a single trunk, but the second-half regime is markedly different in-line with new specifications (Figure 2). For instance, Chords 9 and 10 are nearly identically derived from a random Chord 8, and their close grouping in the new tree is consistent as-such (Figure 2, Right).

Full trial results of all thirty test cases, ten each under the Harmony, Discord $t=21$ break and Discord $t=35$ break frameworks, are listed in Table 5. The DU detection mechanism demonstrated with the two different Discord frameworks consistently shows an accurate identification of the break area, where in both cases a sizable unusualness in the distance of the trees at a threshold above 1 is observed ahead of the $t=21$ and $t=35$ regime breaks (Figure 3). The Harmony DU detection framework does not show any reading above 1, in-line with expectations. The results show the regime shift as being reflected in the standard deviation of the relevant tree distances while the Harmony series reflects stability of regime as expected (Figure 3).

5.2 Financial Market Results

In all three tested cases, the $\bar{\varepsilon}$ measure is able to identify the onset of financial stress in-line with specific known-market event windows (Table 6). Using the known regime-change events as a break within the sample period, returns and standard deviations of the S&P500 are compared pre-and-post break. This is repeated using the regime-change event identified by the phylogenetic tree $\bar{\varepsilon}$ methodology. In the case of the third trial, these breaks are identical where the $\bar{\varepsilon}$ methodology identifies the exact same US inflation data release date as the regime change (Figure 4, Bottom).

In the case of the COVID-19 pandemic, the \mathcal{E} signal identifies the onset of market stress earlier than the March 11th 2020 WHO declaration date (Figure 4, Top Right). In all three cases, returns-over-standard errors post-signal regime change are lower for S&P500 following break events (Figure 5).

5.3 Predictive Results

In all three financial market test cases, the \mathcal{E} measure shows a spike that presages periods of financial distress (Table 7). This translates into a return-over-standard errors outperformance in each predictive trial against the known break dates (Figure 7). Similar to the results of the regime-change identification trial, it appears that information embedded in global macro variable price co-movements ahead of known break events is able to predict distress or at least detect heightened financial market fragility conditions. Each of the three trials demonstrates a \mathcal{E} signal above 1.68. Further testing to refine the interpretation of the scale of the \mathcal{E} signals is out of scope for this paper, but the significance of the results is further evaluated in Section 6.

5.4 Robustness Testing

ARDL optimal lag lengths for PCA and DA variables in each of the three full-sample trials are specified via AIC (Table 8). The residuals for the Taper and CPI trials do not evidence autocorrelation nor residual heteroscedasticity; those of the COVID trial show some evidence of autocorrelation (Table 9). Implementation of the heteroscedasticity-robust ARDL model demonstrates significant results as follows: the Taper trial shows strong explanatory power in the third distance acceleration window, significant at the <0.01% level where a 1% change in DA coincides with a -1.8% change in the PCA (Table 10). The CPI trial evidences similar but more

pronounced effects, where the first and second lags of distance acceleration have significant coefficients of -50.1% and -42.7% respectively (Table 11). Lagged PCA coefficients are significant in both cases, as are the models at the <0.01% levels. The results of the COVID trial are less conclusive where the heteroscedasticity-robust ARDL model is significant (as is the second-lag PCA coefficient) but distance acceleration is not (Table 12). A possible explanation lies in the multiple-sample ε signals observed in the regime-shift methodology (Figure 4, Top Right) where like an internal rate of return (IRR) multiple sign-changes will dampen the detectable signal below the financial-market 1.68 threshold that is primarily relied on.

5.5 Tree Shape

Visual analysis reveals that the shape of the tree itself can lead to important understandings of market conditions. Pre-event trees, in each of the three listed cases, represent multiple ‘branches’ of cross-correlation relationships; post-event trees tend to be much narrower (Figure 8), coinciding with a higher principal component explanatory power in each case (Figure 9). A narrower tree, in other words, means fewer variables are directing the overall model. This is consistent with known studies of high-volatility or market-negative environments where correlations rise around large, disruptive macro factors (Büyüksahin & Robe, 2014). The narrow shape of the tree denotes the higher statistical importance of fewer factors: the better defined a single trunk in a tree is, the more closely the system is moving around said axis. For a tree to exhibit numerous axes, it implies a set of variables that are following various centers of gravity in terms of what their differences are related to. Conversely, a narrow tree has fewer centers of gravity.

5.6 Out of Sample Testing

The February 2022 invasion of the Ukraine by the Russian Federation prompted severe economic sanctions on the Russian economy and currency; the following month saw a 20% decline in the value of the Russian ruble (Figure 10), beginning on the date of the invasion itself, February 24th. The analysis shows that while data from January 3rd 2022 through February 21st 2022 fails to produce a signal, January 3rd through February 22nd produces a \mathcal{E} signal above the 1.68 extremity threshold. The signal immediately precedes the onset of Russian ruble volatility, an extreme downside event for the currency given the effects of global sanctions on the domestic economy. The anticipatory signal that such a shift was about to occur demonstrates the \mathcal{E} methodology's flexibility in mitigating possible tail risk events that are statistically unusual, but also highlights the importance of further testing around inclusive basket composition. Russia does not occupy a large position in global trade, with the exception of mineral exports which make up half of total outbound country activity as of 2020 (Simoes & Hidalgo, 2011), and historically the currency shows very low correlation to global macro factors or to the US dollar index itself; Russian equities comprise less than 2% of the MSCI Emerging Markets basket. Following the invasion, with continued military operations playing a large role in global sentiment expectations given disruptions to energy and food supply chains, the Russian ruble became unusually aligned with global macro risk factors. Given the ruble's historical distance from global macro factors and Russia's relative isolation in global markets, the currency is unlikely to be featured in various portfolio risk construction methods; the test does, however, provides not just a validation of the predictive elements but also a demonstration of the visual analysis methodology where the

dramatic shift in proximity between ruble and global macro risk factors can be seen very clearly in the before-and-after phylogenetic trees (Figure 11). The ruble, in other words, had a long history of moving separately from global markets but became much more prominently linked to other assets in the new regime, precisely what the tree visual analysis demonstrates.

As with any methodology, knowing what to investigate is still an important step in using the phylogenetic tree analysis. Helping practitioners to choose what to measure is a design element that phylogenetic tree analysis can deliver in a visually concise and appealing manner.

5.7 Proposed Implementation Framework Results

Applying the framework to a sample S&P 500 long-short portfolio in first-half 2023 data yields profitable results. The portfolio notionally outperforms the index by 1.87% at a $\bar{\epsilon}$ extremity threshold of 1.00, and by 5.23% at a threshold of 1.68 (Figure 12). On a Sharpe ratio basis, both the 1.00 and 1.68 extremity thresholds show outperformance of +0.72% and +2.02% over the S&P 500 respectively (Table 13). Both $\bar{\epsilon}$ extremity threshold portfolio runs outperform equity thematic ETF products on a Sharpe ratio basis over this sample period as well, including momentum, emerging market, value, quality and minimum volatility strategy ETFs (Table 14).

6. Discussion on Implications

A wide variety of use-cases can be identified with both the visual analysis and regime-break indicator applications of this framework; these include Environment, Sustainability and Governance (ESG) factor analysis, currency sensitivity analysis, equity market hedging and even non-financial operations. Areas for further exploration include sensitivity testing of the distance unusualness threshold and tree basket construction itself. What factors are included in the analysis

is of course important to understanding its results, where the exclusion of certain variables may fundamentally change the outcomes. These are all presented as avenues for further research.

6.1 Visual Analysis

It is important for financial market practitioners to understand what factors are affecting various assets, be they individual securities, commodities, currencies or even portfolios. The Russian ruble example, for instance, provides a demonstration of a detailed yet clear and succinct view of how a financial time series measure's relationship to other factors can dramatically change within a complex environment. Understanding the relationship of changes in one variable to changes in another variable or set of variables is a major thrust of statistical analysis, and this paper offers a novel visual tool for practitioners and researchers to more effectively analyze large sets of data across a broad set of fields. Financial markets themselves are always changing, and understanding the current environment is often an extraordinarily time-sensitive task for fund managers, traders and other stakeholders. Contributions to expanding the field of visual analysis alone, in this vein, is known to be an important component of financial research and as such we expect these specific implications of this paper's work to be significant.

6.2 Predictive Applications

The predictive applications of understanding when relationships between variables are changing, particularly as these regime shifts tend to herald periods of market disturbance, is the most obviously urgent outcome of this paper. Markets are constantly changing but detecting periods of chaos before the storm implies a certain knowledge of upcoming regime-changes in markets themselves. This does not necessarily imply insider-trading phenomena or instances of inefficient

markets. As the experienced sailor may sense a gathering storm and change course accordingly, market prices themselves demonstrate a degree of foresight. Whether this is a self-fulfilling prophecy or a form of market efficiency is a matter of future debate, but providing access to tools that are able to quantitatively describe these conditions can help to predict periods where markets are becoming more susceptible to or are anticipating periods of change. In this formulation, the Ξ measure may be considered as a ‘market fragility’ indicator where prices reflect shifting conditions; investor uncertainty is recognized as largely a market-negative phenomenon that can describe similar precursors to financial turbulence. Future research may help to define specific contributions to market efficiency further. The proposed implementation framework shows that this signal can be developed not just for risk mitigation but also for profit generation purposes.

There is another important aspect to this contribution where a known vulnerability of financial modeling is the knowledge that at some point the unexpected occurs, and those exogenous shocks shift the underlying meaning of variables and/or constants. Under this formulation of phylogenetic tree analysis, the methodological vulnerability is the *exclusion* of variables, but aside from this the ability to detect *when* financial models in general may come under stress is itself significant. This framework offers practitioners and researchers the ability to identify periods where the underlying assumptions underpinning financial models are beginning to change. The early detection of such ‘earthquakes’ is not necessarily limited to financial modeling.

7. Conclusions

Phylogenetic trees are shown to be effective tools at visual statistical analysis and can also forecast regime change in financial markets based on the unusualness of the rate of change in the shape of the trees. This paper is designed to demonstrate this effectiveness, and to open the field of research to more investigation and use-cases of phylogenetic trees. There are financial market-safety applications that are directly discussed, though any case where a visually concise understanding of the relationship between time series variables in a complex system may be helpful can benefit from these frameworks.

This research, demonstrating effectiveness at identifying regime-shifts from known U.S. macro-economic shifts, should be applied to other geographic markets and asset classes in future studies. Proposed future areas of study include the formalization of a scale of severity for Ξ signals, making these ‘early earthquake warning’ measures more broadly interpretable to practitioners and researchers. Additionally, evaluating whether these Ξ signal scales of severity are universal or are context-dependent is an important step in determining new use cases for the predictive qualities of phylogenetic tree shape-changes. There are numerous refinements and optimizations that can be applied to this methodology that the authors are currently limited in exploring due to the computing power required to run both phylogenetic tree analysis and regime-shift detection processes; these optimizations include time-window sensitivity, optimal number of factors, data frequency and alternative computational methods. As long as we do not lose the forest for the trees, there is much information that has yet to be gleaned from the lush foliage of this analytical methodology.

Appendix

Table 1

List of Variables Used in the Empirical Analysis

Variable ID	Asset Class	Frequency	Short ID	Description (All in US Dollars)	Bloomberg Source Ticker
R_DXY_D	Currency	Daily	DXY	US Dollar Index	DXY Curncy (USD)
R_AUD_D	Currency	Daily	AUD	Australian Dollar (Spot)	AUDUSD Curncy (USD)
R_XAU_D	Commodity	Daily	Gold	Gold (Spot)	XAU Curncy (USD)
R_XPT_D	Commodity	Daily	Plat	Platinum (Spot)	XPT Curncy (USD)
R_XAG_D	Commodity	Daily	Silv	Silver (Spot)	XAG Curncy (USD)
R_JPY_D	Currency	Daily	JPY	Japanese Yen (Spot)	JPYUSD Curncy (USD)
R_ZAR_D	Currency	Daily	ZAR	South African Rand (Spot)	ZARUSD Curncy (USD)
R_TRY_D	Currency	Daily	TRY	Turkish Lira (Spot)	TRYUSD Curncy (USD)
R_MXN_D	Currency	Daily	MXN	Mexican Peso (Spot)	MXNUSD Curncy (USD)
R_NZD_D	Currency	Daily	NZD	New Zealand Dollar (Spot)	NZDUSD Curncy (USD)
R_CAD_D	Currency	Daily	CAD	Canadian Dollar (Spot)	CADUSD Curncy (USD)
R_EUR_D	Currency	Daily	EUR	Euro (Spot)	EURUSD Curncy (USD)
R_GBP_D	Currency	Daily	GBP	British Pound (Spot)	GBPUSD Curncy (USD)
R_Oil_D	Commodity	Daily	Oil	WTI 1st Crude Oil	CL1 Comdty (USD)
R_NOK_D	Currency	Daily	NOK	Norwegian Krone (Spot)	NOKUSD Curncy (USD)
R_SEK_D	Currency	Daily	SEK	Swedish Krona (Spot)	SEKUSD Curncy (USD)
R_CHF_D	Currency	Daily	CHF	Swiss Franc (Spot)	CHFUSD Curncy (USD)
R_PLN_D	Currency	Daily	PLN	Polish Zloty (Spot)	PLNUSD Curncy (USD)
R_US55_D	Rates	Daily	US55	USD Inflation Swap Forward 5year-5year	FWISUS55 Index (USD)
R_US10_D	Rates	Daily	US10	US 10year Treasury Yields	USGG10YR Index (USD)
R_MXEF_D	Equity	Daily	MXEF	MSCI Emerging Markets	MXEF Index (USD)
R_MXEU_D	Equity	Daily	MXEU	MSCI Europe	MXEU Index (USD)
R_MXWO_D	Equity	Daily	MXWO	MSCI World	MXWO Index (USD)
R_SPX_D	Equity	Daily	SPX	S&P500	SPX Index (USD)
R_RUB_D	Currency	Daily	RUB	Russian Ruble (Spot)	RUBUSD Curncy (USD)
R_MTUM_D	Equity	Daily	MTUM	iShares MSCI USA Momentum Factor ETF	MTUM US Equity (USD)
R_EEM_D	Equity	Daily	EEM	iShares MSCI Emerging Markets ETF	EEM US Equity (USD)
R_IWM_D	Equity	Daily	IWM	iShares Russell 2000 ETF	IWM US Equity (USD)
R_VLUE_D	Equity	Daily	VLUE	iShares MSCI USA Value Factor ETF	VLUE US Equity (USD)
R_QUAL_D	Equity	Daily	QUAL	iShares MSCI USA Quality Factor ETF	QUAL US Equity (USD)
R_USMV_D	Equity	Daily	USMV	iShares MSCI USA Minimum Volatility Factor ETF	USMV US Equity (USD)

Note. All data is daily end-of-day mid-market price, sampled historically 2012-1H 2023 in US dollars. Russian ruble is only included in out-of-sample testing.

Table 2

Full Sample Descriptive Statistics of Market Returns

Short ID	N	Mean	St Dev	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
DXY	3089	0.007%	0.370%	-2.372%	2.052%	0.041	2.929
AUD	3089	-0.010%	0.550%	-3.825%	2.182%	-0.237	2.855
G	3089	0.008%	0.848%	-9.074%	5.092%	-0.604	8.827
Plat	3089	-0.005%	1.277%	-12.749%	10.619%	-0.378	8.246
Silv	3089	0.004%	1.506%	-14.887%	8.002%	-0.552	10.171
JPY	3089	-0.011%	0.495%	-3.424%	3.885%	0.174	7.001
ZAR	3089	-0.018%	0.879%	-4.704%	5.246%	-0.198	1.935
TRY	3089	-0.060%	0.884%	-13.651%	8.552%	-1.731	37.557
MXN	3089	-0.011%	0.714%	-7.692%	4.306%	-0.659	7.515
NZD	3089	-0.003%	0.581%	-3.465%	2.491%	-0.134	2.011
CAD	3089	-0.006%	0.417%	-2.088%	1.996%	0.011	2.238
EUR	3089	-0.004%	0.441%	-2.354%	3.062%	0.113	3.327
GBP	3089	-0.004%	0.500%	-8.053%	3.046%	-1.373	25.054
Oil	3089	-0.101%	6.455%	-305.966%	37.662%	-36.818	1682.008
NOK	3089	-0.011%	0.642%	-7.128%	4.171%	-0.794	9.119
SEK	3089	-0.008%	0.546%	-3.755%	2.344%	-0.191	2.620
CHF	3089	0.002%	0.591%	-2.387%	21.526%	15.638	568.555
PLN	3089	-0.004%	0.604%	-4.484%	3.276%	-0.106	3.237
US55	3089	0.011%	1.648%	-15.829%	17.584%	0.075	16.117
US10	3089	0.032%	2.895%	-29.070%	50.153%	2.436	64.615
MXEF	3089	0.013%	0.869%	-6.707%	5.732%	-0.528	6.250
MXEU	3089	0.020%	0.971%	-12.357%	8.585%	-0.938	15.295
MXWO	3089	0.035%	0.796%	-9.915%	8.770%	-1.142	26.681
SPX	3089	0.047%	0.928%	-11.984%	9.383%	-0.693	25.799
RUB*	70	0.081%	4.961%	-20.168%	14.634%	-0.592	4.458
MTUM	107	0.005%	0.863%	-1.910%	2.007%	-0.034	-0.382
EEM	107	0.010%	0.952%	-2.246%	2.145%	-0.153	-0.242
IWM	107	0.027%	1.300%	-2.951%	3.627%	-0.099	-0.042
VLUE	107	0.008%	1.024%	-2.373%	1.986%	-0.113	-0.729
QUAL	107	0.126%	0.974%	-2.150%	2.361%	0.028	-0.494
USMV	107	0.026%	0.652%	-1.369%	1.406%	0.024	-0.442

Note. All descriptive statistics are taken from January 2nd, 2012 to December 13th, 2021 with the exception of Russian ruble (*) where only relevant out-of-sample data from January 3rd, 2022 to 8th May, 2022 is used. Variables marked (**) are sampled from 18th January, 2023 to 15th June, 2023. Non-I(1) variables are excluded from PCA construction, Tables 10-12.

Table 3

Dickey-Fuller (ADF stationary, k:5) unit root test results for In- Sample Time Series Returns and Levels

Variable	Test statistic (level)	p-value (level)	Test statistic (return)	p-value (return)
DXY	-2.129	0.2328	-46.543***	<0.0001
AUD	-2.072	0.2560	-47.673***	<0.0001
XAU	-0.994	0.7555	-49.585 ***	<0.0001
XPT	-1.609	0.4789	-47.640***	<0.0001
XAG	-1.755	0.4031	-50.430***	<0.0001
JPY	-4.220***	0.0006	-47.500***	<0.0001
ZAR	-2.128	0.2334	-47.309***	<0.0001
TRY	-0.218	0.9363	-44.522***	<0.0001
MXN	-0.579	0.8756	-48.482***	<0.0001
NZD	-2.166	0.2187	-48.123***	<0.0001
CAD	-2.268	0.1824	-47.285***	<0.0001
EUR	-1.862	0.3499	-47.393***	<0.0001
GBP	-1.547	0.5100	-45.034***	<0.0001
Oil	-2.389	0.1449	-38.884***	<0.0001
NOK	-1.973	0.2984	-47.101***	<0.0001
SEK	-1.849	0.3564	-48.597***	<0.0001
CHF	-4.034***	0.0012	-51.639***	<0.0001
PLN	-1.353	0.6046	-47.367***	<0.0001
US55	-3.795***	0.0030	-60.030***	<0.0001
US10	-1.612	0.4772	-54.433***	<0.0001
MXEF	-1.538	0.5145	-43.511***	<0.0001
MXEU	-2.096	0.2460	-48.506***	<0.0001
MXWO	-0.115	0.9479	-49.752***	<0.0001
SPX	0.238	0.9743	-57.304***	<0.0001

Note. All testing occurs over the January 2nd, 2012 to December 13th, 2021 daily data sample window.

Table 4

Market Return Cross Correlation Analysis

	R_DXY_D	R_AUD_D	R_AU_D	R_MPT_D	R_XAG_D	R_MPT_D	R_ZAR_D	R_TRY_D	R_MXN_D	R_NZD_D	R_CAD_D	R_EUR_D	R_GBP_D	R_Oil_D	R_NOK_D	R_SEK_D	R_CHE_D	R_PLN_D	R_USS_D	R_USD_D	R_MXEF_D	R_MXEU_D	R_MXWO_D	R_SPX_D
R_DXY_D	1.000																							
R_AUD_D	-0.536	1.000																						
R_AU_D	-0.418	0.344	1.000																					
R_MPT_D	-0.351	0.432	0.607	1.000																				
R_XAG_D	-0.367	0.397	0.799	0.664	1.000																			
R_MPT_D	-0.479	0.199	0.386	0.133	0.201	1.000																		
R_ZAR_D	-0.378	0.578	0.230	0.356	0.299	0.084	1.000																	
R_TRY_D	-0.233	0.315	0.146	0.213	0.175	0.031	0.409	1.000																
R_MXN_D	-0.307	0.524	0.165	0.305	0.250	-0.001	0.620	0.351	1.000															
R_NZD_D	-0.547	0.787	0.354	0.381	0.368	0.528	0.521	0.285	0.459	1.000														
R_CAD_D	-0.472	0.646	0.258	0.385	0.336	0.090	0.519	0.286	0.520	0.584	1.000													
R_EUR_D	-0.920	0.474	0.361	0.305	0.315	0.354	0.345	0.221	0.284	0.484	0.390	1.000												
R_GBP_D	-0.647	0.488	0.235	0.258	0.254	0.190	0.346	0.190	0.337	0.469	0.426	0.550	1.000											
R_Oil_D	-0.041	0.106	0.020	0.097	0.067	-0.053	0.083	0.040	0.122	0.074	0.190	0.021	0.080	1.000										
R_NOK_D	-0.643	0.599	0.296	0.417	0.354	0.155	0.488	0.270	0.474	0.562	0.571	0.621	0.503	0.170	1.000									
R_SEK_D	-0.743	0.538	0.318	0.348	0.325	0.228	0.413	0.246	0.366	0.523	0.456	0.745	0.513	0.077	0.721	1.000								
R_CHE_D	-0.599	0.299	0.345	0.225	0.242	0.370	0.178	0.090	0.120	0.336	0.236	0.585	0.342	-0.007	0.385	0.460	1.000							
R_PLN_D	-0.771	0.543	0.319	0.344	0.337	0.221	0.491	0.302	0.447	0.522	0.468	0.813	0.535	0.047	0.621	0.684	0.445	1.000						
R_USS_D	-0.048	0.128	0.012	0.088	0.036	-0.092	0.083	0.032	0.088	0.081	0.108	0.039	0.124	0.041	0.129	0.107	0.003	0.080	1.000					
R_USD_D	0.145	0.060	-0.238	0.021	-0.077	-0.451	0.086	0.066	0.121	-0.021	0.117	-0.068	-0.009	0.126	0.102	-0.007	-0.184	-0.011	0.148	1.000				
R_MXEF_D	-0.136	0.385	0.075	0.323	0.225	-0.172	0.392	0.215	0.358	0.291	0.349	0.101	0.211	0.111	0.351	0.239	0.037	0.263	0.199	0.214	1.000			
R_MXEU_D	-0.309	0.445	0.083	0.343	0.229	-0.181	0.395	0.236	0.407	0.380	0.442	0.276	0.381	0.122	0.498	0.391	0.126	0.413	0.211	0.287	0.648	1.000		
R_MXWO_D	-0.134	0.455	0.061	0.369	0.232	-0.205	0.430	0.230	0.494	0.361	0.464	0.117	0.268	0.173	0.464	0.394	0.002	0.307	0.219	0.434	0.633	0.783	1.000	
R_SPX_D	-0.027	0.382	0.017	0.307	0.177	-0.332	0.390	0.197	0.470	0.284	0.407	0.030	0.177	0.167	0.371	0.208	-0.065	0.221	0.191	0.458	0.469	0.584	0.945	1.000

Note. All testing occurs over the January 2nd, 2012 to December 13th, 2021 daily data sample window.

Table 5

Harmony versus Discord test results

Harmony											
t	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Trial 6	Trial 7	Trial 8	Trial 9	Trial 10	Average
13	1.103	1.148	1.709	1.626	0.535	1.018	0.657	1.445	0.626	0.183	1.005
14	0.912	0.697	1.660	0.574	0.452	0.867	0.639	1.512	0.608	0.273	0.819
15	0.914	0.733	1.513	0.584	0.419	0.737	0.586	1.561	0.590	0.323	0.796
16	0.865	0.792	0.219	0.537	0.247	0.879	0.500	1.615	0.386	0.293	0.633
17	0.794	0.853	0.254	0.426	0.173	0.956	0.252	1.655	0.386	0.637	0.639
18	0.803	0.929	0.266	0.323	0.188	0.947	0.242	1.659	0.369	0.857	0.658
19	0.847	1.125	0.280	0.252	0.207	0.964	0.414	1.648	0.298	0.922	0.696
20	0.906	1.114	0.252	0.213	0.310	0.933	0.475	1.590	0.271	1.146	0.721
21	0.916	1.077	0.235	0.236	0.370	0.797	0.416	0.030	0.254	1.321	0.565
22	0.834	0.795	0.210	0.230	0.389	0.754	0.440	0.030	0.217	1.412	0.531
23	0.267	0.530	0.183	0.204	0.394	0.705	0.437	0.027	1.490	1.560	0.580
24	0.388	0.546	0.208	0.192	0.398	0.707	0.426	0.033	1.482	1.555	0.593
25	0.446	0.545	0.182	0.166	0.406	0.564	0.408	0.037	1.490	1.576	0.582
26	0.460	0.546	0.258	0.166	1.639	0.570	0.371	0.037	1.495	1.616	0.716
27	0.422	0.578	0.305	0.244	1.611	0.655	0.286	0.037	1.494	1.537	0.717
28	0.374	0.614	0.346	0.231	1.583	0.791	0.106	0.043	1.497	1.430	0.701
29	0.373	0.585	0.356	0.229	1.564	0.729	0.070	0.049	1.499	1.432	0.688
30	0.730	0.592	0.351	0.250	1.572	0.805	0.081	0.050	1.538	1.320	0.729
31	0.865	0.584	0.328	0.254	1.584	0.922	0.107	0.049	1.564	0.921	0.718
32	0.921	0.577	0.295	0.223	1.599	1.006	0.093	0.130	1.631	0.901	0.738
33	0.925	0.490	0.287	0.231	1.614	1.063	0.262	0.130	0.435	0.826	0.626
34	0.880	0.488	0.262	0.207	1.632	1.084	1.511	0.138	0.443	0.854	0.750
35	0.825	0.376	0.262	0.134	1.647	1.082	1.509	0.141	0.457	0.837	0.727
36	0.752	0.521	0.273	0.085	0.083	1.133	1.496	0.145	0.714	0.804	0.601
37	1.165	0.538	0.281	0.194	0.100	1.227	1.467	0.166	0.739	0.914	0.679

Discord t=21											
t	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Trial 6	Trial 7	Trial 8	Trial 9	Trial 10	Average
13	0.234	0.147	0.391	0.168	0.756	0.491	0.294	0.738	0.455	0.494	0.417
14	0.250	0.226	0.401	0.164	0.362	0.446	0.276	0.732	0.449	0.834	0.414
15	0.467	0.287	0.407	0.966	0.593	0.390	0.438	0.703	0.487	0.967	0.571
16	0.593	0.307	0.394	0.995	0.677	0.277	0.594	0.706	0.577	1.011	0.613
17	0.738	0.314	0.459	1.057	0.624	0.335	0.557	0.661	0.518	0.955	0.622
18	0.868	0.326	0.426	1.551	0.905	0.318	0.846	1.543	0.440	1.028	0.825
19	1.167	1.734	1.245	1.500	1.228	1.562	0.988	1.538	1.073	1.081	1.312
20	1.200	1.742	1.244	1.443	1.281	1.620	1.198	1.565	1.297	1.222	1.381
21	1.213	1.742	1.247	1.473	1.286	1.636	1.449	1.563	1.352	1.265	1.423
22	1.277	1.755	1.245	1.498	1.352	1.636	1.449	1.545	1.473	1.311	1.454
23	1.358	1.773	1.245	1.538	1.377	1.672	1.644	1.549	1.513	1.294	1.496
24	1.378	1.791	1.218	1.573	1.384	1.686	1.702	1.556	1.613	1.300	1.520
25	1.397	1.808	1.213	1.473	1.363	1.692	1.631	1.559	1.670	1.277	1.508
26	1.423	1.815	1.202	1.502	1.394	1.692	1.492	1.532	1.625	1.253	1.493
27	1.413	1.822	1.199	1.467	1.438	1.720	1.421	1.531	1.620	1.242	1.487
28	1.323	1.828	1.201	0.427	1.265	1.743	0.836	0.213	1.575	1.054	1.147
29	0.867	0.214	0.687	0.355	0.427	0.334	0.900	0.213	0.542	0.607	0.515
30	0.840	0.217	0.821	0.156	0.404	0.352	0.927	0.279	0.617	0.488	0.508
31	0.815	0.216	0.801	0.154	0.412	0.325	0.885	0.325	0.703	0.438	0.507
32	0.732	0.210	0.833	0.139	0.459	0.251	0.826	0.326	0.723	0.463	0.496
33	0.612	0.178	0.773	0.264	0.506	0.263	0.648	0.321	0.746	0.450	0.476
34	0.546	0.166	0.790	0.322	0.541	0.266	0.596	0.585	0.754	0.470	0.503
35	0.455	0.153	0.786	0.332	0.350	0.274	0.581	0.592	0.665	0.474	0.466
36	0.355	0.160	0.887	0.318	0.366	0.275	0.578	0.621	0.519	0.480	0.456
37	0.781	0.160	0.915	0.306	0.373	0.409	0.680	0.655	0.456	0.567	0.530

Discord t=35											
t	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Trial 6	Trial 7	Trial 8	Trial 9	Trial 10	Average
13	0.091	0.210	0.355	0.488	0.384	0.419	0.078	0.185	0.100	0.648	0.296
14	0.108	0.228	0.308	0.175	0.396	0.424	0.075	0.183	0.094	0.903	0.289
15	0.158	0.247	0.273	0.173	0.485	0.581	0.067	0.169	0.104	0.866	0.312
16	0.178	0.279	0.208	0.167	0.484	0.603	0.048	0.159	0.097	0.858	0.308
17	0.199	0.272	0.348	0.211	0.441	0.583	0.028	0.373	0.106	0.852	0.341
18	0.205	0.263	0.363	0.214	0.538	0.712	0.024	0.426	0.120	0.830	0.369
19	0.219	0.282	0.412	0.243	0.525	0.636	0.024	0.487	0.114	0.870	0.381
20	0.216	0.284	0.453	0.244	0.423	0.632	0.026	0.532	0.216	0.894	0.392
21	0.242	0.264	0.452	0.283	0.459	0.494	0.031	0.521	0.279	0.938	0.396
22	0.259	0.252	0.503	0.279	0.522	0.477	0.033	0.509	0.423	0.977	0.423
23	0.343	0.227	0.501	0.295	0.402	0.505	0.034	0.459	0.499	1.024	0.429
24	0.298	0.195	0.564	0.293	0.378	0.705	0.065	0.456	0.566	0.582	0.410
25	0.297	0.201	0.772	0.317	0.427	0.841	0.078	0.414	0.588	0.535	0.447
26	0.348	0.160	0.848	0.544	0.426	0.934	0.108	0.328	0.557	0.472	0.472
27	0.404	0.158	0.899	0.633	0.425	0.992	0.360	0.532	0.826	0.339	0.557
28	0.395	0.153	1.336	0.788	0.402	1.002	0.426	0.542	0.849	0.454	0.635
29	0.958	0.316	1.336	0.853	0.864	1.101	0.446	0.536	1.013	0.799	0.822
30	0.936	0.467	1.352	0.886	0.863	1.139	0.878	0.839	0.994	0.797	0.915
31	0.931	0.466	1.386	0.994	0.833	1.082	1.502	0.844	1.109	0.799	0.994
32	1.269	1.174	1.380	0.942	1.155	0.921	1.459	1.334	1.100	1.146	1.188
33	1.273	1.303	1.566	0.859	1.258	0.364	1.403	1.440	1.088	1.132	1.169
34	1.312	1.272	1.585	0.769	1.381	0.359	1.382	1.590	1.151	1.166	1.197
35	1.326	1.216	1.566	0.853	1.372	0.374	1.325	1.721	1.233	1.160	1.214
36	1.318	1.153	1.536	0.886	1.427	0.399	1.265	1.712	1.279	1.248	1.222
37	1.313	1.234	1.611	1.282	1.422	0.356	1.273	1.747	1.158	1.235	1.263

Note. All results indicate the standardized tree Distance Unusualness (DU) measure reading for each time series instance where each trial is run using a newly generated set of random variables where applicable and under various break (Discord) or no-break (Harmony) conditions.

Table 6

Regime-Shift Identification Results

Taper Regime Shifts				
State	Pre (Known Break)	Post (Known Break)	Pre (Ξ Signal)	Post (Ξ Signal)
Average SPX Return	0.16%	-0.10%	0.14%	0.02%
Return Standard Deviation	0.65%	1.01%	0.80%	0.85%
COVID-19 Regime Shifts				
State	Pre (Known Break)	Post (Known Break)	Pre (Ξ Signal)	Post (Ξ Signal)
Average SPX Return	-0.51%	0.29%	0.10%	-0.20%
Return Standard Deviation	3.34%	4.00%	0.85%	4.28%
CPI Regime Shifts				
State	Pre (Known Break)	Post (Known Break)	Pre (Ξ Signal)	Post (Ξ Signal)
Average SPX Return	0.19%	-0.05%	0.19%	-0.05%
Return Standard Deviation	0.40%	1.43%	0.40%	1.43%

Note. All results indicate the returns and return standard deviations of S&P500 before and after known regime breaks versus Ξ -identified regime breaks.

Table 7

Regime-Shift Predictive Results

Taper Regime Shifts				
State	Pre (Known Break)	Post (Known Break)	Pre (Ξ Signal)	Post (Ξ Signal)
Average SPX Return	0.16%	-0.10%	0.22%	-0.08%
Return Standard Deviation	0.65%	1.01%	0.67%	0.92%
COVID-19 Regime Shifts				
State	Pre (Known Break)	Post (Known Break)	Pre (Ξ Signal)	Post (Ξ Signal)
Average SPX Return	-0.51%	0.29%	0.08%	-0.17%
Return Standard Deviation	3.34%	4.00%	1.02%	4.04%
CPI Regime Shifts				
State	Pre (Known Break)	Post (Known Break)	Pre (Ξ Signal)	Post (Ξ Signal)
Average SPX Return	0.19%	-0.05%	0.24%	-0.01%
Return Standard Deviation	0.40%	1.43%	0.43%	1.10%

Note. All results indicate the returns and return standard deviations of S&P500 before and after known regime breaks versus Ξ -identified regime breaks using only pre-break data.

Table 8

Lag selection order criteria

Taper									
Lag	LL	LR	df	p	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBC	
0	-25.5615				5.7962*	4.9432*	4.5792*	4.6466*	
1	-26.5814	0.36815	1	0.544	6.6585	4.73023	4.70011	4.81105	
2	-26.021	0.72075	1	0.396	7.46173	4.83384	4.79196	4.95807	
3	-25.9527	0.13663	1	0.712	8.8327	4.99112	4.93228	5.15736	
4	-25.9516	0.00233	1	0.962	10.7476	5.15859	5.08379	5.36964	
Distance									
Lag	LL	LR	df	p	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBC	
0	6.29516				0.022368	-0.962757	-0.98558	-0.926584	
1	6.49238	0.39443	1	0.530	0.023976	-0.816796	-0.862399	-0.744452	
2	6.53681	0.08887	1	0.766	0.031218	-0.643057	-0.711462	-0.53454	
3	6.65628	0.23893	1	0.625	0.037404	-0.482959	-0.574166	-0.33827	
4	12.2744	11.236*	1	0.081	0.07676*	-1.32261*	-1.43662*	-1.14175*	

COVID									
Lag	LL	LR	df	p	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBC	
0	-19.5608				0.90131	2.7424	2.7374	2.78144	
1	-19.5051	0.00441	1	0.953	1.03355	2.86735	2.86634	2.96175	
2	-19.3408	0.32861	1	0.366	1.15761	2.97877	2.97726	3.12038	
3	-1.3284	36.022*	1	0.000	-1.20761*	-7.0046*	-7.08635*	-6.99459*	
4	-0.925403	0.80888	1	0.368	0.132477	0.790054	0.78354	1.02607	
Distance									
Lag	LL	LR	df	p	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBC	
0	11.5789				0.012925	-1.51098	-1.51521	-1.46534	
1	16.4609	9.7841*	1	0.002	0.007425	-2.06699	-2.07544	-1.9757	
2	18.0725	3.2071	1	0.073	0.06844*	-2.15321*	-2.16589*	-2.01627*	
3	18.2304	0.31383	1	0.574	0.007794	-2.03292	-2.04982	-1.85033	
4	18.4108	0.36088	1	0.348	0.008908	-1.91582	-1.93695	-1.68759	

CPI									
Lag	LL	LR	df	p	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBC	
0	-20.0484				3.94512	4.20968	4.17669	4.23994	
1	-19.0765	1.9438	1	0.163	3.98644	4.21531	4.14892	4.27583	
2	-18.1041	1.945	1	0.163	4.06321	4.22081	4.12123	4.31159	
3	-4.26363	23.673*	1	0.000	4.04522*	-2.05439*	-1.92076*	-2.15466*	
4	-6.06598	0.40331	1	0.525	0.590924	-2.2132	-2.04723	-2.36449	
Distance									
Lag	LL	LR	df	p	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBC	
0	5.64907				0.018337	-1.16227	-1.22924	-1.15234	
1	6.17275	1.0474	1	0.306	0.020853	-1.04319	-1.17114	-1.02353	
2	8.00018	3.6549	1	0.056	0.07432*	-1.25005*	-1.45097*	-1.22025*	
3	8.14568	0.29101	1	0.590	0.022921	-1.03642	-1.30432	-0.9967	
4	8.33146	0.37155	1	0.542	0.031686	-0.832865	-1.16774	-0.783214	

Note. (*) representing optimal lag length. Endogenous = rPCA & tree distance first difference, exogenous = constant

Table 9

ARDL \tilde{PCA} , DA Short Run Model Breusch-Godfrey LM Test for Autocorrelation and White's Test for Unrestricted Heteroscedasticity

Taper			
lags (p)	chi2	df	Prob>chi2
1	<0.001	1	1.0000
chi2(9)= 11.00			
Prob > chi(2)= 0.3575			
COVID			
lags (p)	chi2	df	Prob>chi2
1	4.145	1	0.0418**
chi2(9)= 28.00			
Prob > chi(2)= 0.4110			
CPI			
lags (p)	chi2	df	Prob>chi2
1	1.296	1	0.2549
chi2(9)= 16.00			
Prob > chi(2)= 0.3821			

Note. Breusch-Godfrey H0 = no serial autocorrelation. White's test for H0: homoscedasticity, against * Ha: unrestricted heteroscedasticity. $\tilde{}$ represents dependent variable.

Table 10

Taper ARDL ~PCA, DA Short Run Model with Robust Standard Errors

Model Parameters ARDL (1,4)						
Total Observations	11					
Prob > F	<0.0001					
R-Squared	0.9507***					
Root MSE	1.1516					
Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t	P> t	Lower Bound (95%)	Upper Bound (95%)
rPCA						
λ_1	-1.0426**	0.2395	-4.35	0.012	-1.7075	-0.3778
DA						
β_0	0.1276	0.2696	0.47	0.661	-0.6209	0.8760
β_1	-0.0620	0.2091	-0.30	0.782	-0.6426	0.5186
β_2	0.0494	0.1315	0.38	0.726	-0.3157	0.4145
β_3	0.0801	0.1010	0.79	0.472	-0.2003	0.3605
β_4	-0.0175***	0.0011	-15.79	<0.001	-0.0206	-0.0144
γ_0	-0.2226	0.4021	-0.55	0.609	-1.3391	0.8939

Note. ***, **, * represents significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively. $\tilde{\cdot}$ represents dependent variable. Adjustment refers to error correction term. α are variable coefficients, and p,q refer to lags of dependent and exogenous variables respectively. rPCA refers to lagged PCA returns and DA to lagged distance acceleration.

Table 11

CPI ARDL ~PCA, DA Short Run Model with Robust Standard Errors

Model Parameters ARDL (3,2)						
Total Observations	20.14					
Prob > F	<0.0001					
R-Squared	0.8708***					
Root MSE	2.6207					
Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t	P> t	Lower Bound (95%)	Upper Bound (95%)
rPCA						
λ_1	2.9192	1.6157	1.81	0.104	-0.7358	6.5741
λ_2	-4.2504**	1.7251	-2.46	0.036	-8.1528	-0.3480
λ_3	0.3258	0.2142	1.52	0.163	-0.1587	0.8103
DA						
β_0	0.6023	0.4088	1.47	0.175	-0.3224	1.5270
β_1	-0.5010*	0.2587	-1.94	0.085	-1.0862	0.0842
β_2	-0.4172**	0.1552	-2.69	0.025	-0.7683	-0.0662
γ_0	0.9524	0.7218	1.32	0.220	-0.6805	2.5852

Note. ***, **, * represents significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively. $\tilde{\cdot}$ represents dependent variable. Adjustment refers to error correction term. α are variable coefficients, and p,q refer to lags of dependent and exogenous variables respectively. rPCA refers to lagged PCA returns and DA to lagged distance acceleration.

Table 12

COVID ARDL ~PCA, DA Short Run Model with Robust Standard Errors

Model Parameters ARDL (3,2)						
Total Observations	28					
Prob > F	<0.0001					
R-Squared	0.7332***					
Root MSE	1.1516					
Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t	P> t	Lower Bound (95%)	Upper Bound (95%)
rPCA						
λ_1	0.2730	1.4077	0.19	0.848	-2.6546	3.2005
λ_2	-1.0459	1.4389	-0.73	0.475	-4.0382	1.9465
λ_3	-1.8453**	0.6997	-2.64	0.015	-3.3004	-0.3901
DA						
β_0	-0.4816	0.3888	-1.24	0.229	-1.2902	0.3269
β_1	0.3721	0.3168	1.17	0.253	-0.2867	1.0309
β_2	0.3995	0.3465	1.15	0.262	-0.3210	1.1200
γ_0	-0.9104	0.7049	-1.29	0.211	-2.3762	0.5555

Note. ***, **, * represents significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively. $\tilde{}$ represents dependent variable.

Adjustment refers to error correction term. α are variable coefficients, and p,q refer to lags of dependent and exogenous variables respectively. rPCA refers to lagged PCA returns and DA to lagged distance acceleration.

Table 13

Performance Analysis of S&P 500 Portfolio Returns with Ξ Signal Application

	Portfolio ($\Xi > 1.00$)	Portfolio ($\Xi > 1.68$)	S&P 500
Average Return - Risk Free	0.02%	0.04%	0.00%
Return Standard Deviation	2.14%	2.10%	2.12%
Sharpe Ratio	0.78%	2.09%	0.07%

Note. Portfolios model, with transaction and slippage costs, long S&P 500 during non-signal periods and short during signal periods based on Ξ extremity thresholds. Risk free rate is taken as US generic government 10 year yields.

Table 14

Exchange Traded Fund (ETF) Sharpe Ratio vs. Portfolio Returns with Ξ Signal Application

Sharpe Ratio Performance Over Benchmarks	MTUM	EEM	IWM	VLUE	QUAL	USMV
Against Portfolio ($\Xi > 1.00$)	-6.09%	-5.46%	-5.00%	-5.94%	-0.21%	-4.89%
Against Portfolio ($\Xi > 1.68$)	-7.39%	-6.77%	-6.30%	-7.24%	-1.51%	-6.19%
Against S&P 500	-5.37%	-4.74%	-4.28%	-5.22%	0.51%	-4.17%

Note. ETF Sharpe ratios are measured notionally against those of portfolios models which, with transaction and slippage costs, are long S&P 500 during non-signal periods and short during signal periods based on Ξ extremity thresholds. Risk free rate is taken as US generic government 10 year yields.

Figure 1. A 'harmonic system' under Harmony specifications where all Chord (C) variables are algebraically derived from the same random Theme variable.

Figure 2. A system where the first half of the time series operates under Harmony specifications and all Chord (C) variables are algebraically derived from the same random Theme variable (Left) but the second half of the time series operates under more varied Discord rules (Right). The Harmonic tree is very nearly linear along a single ‘trunk’ as all Chords derive from the single Theme variable, whereas the Discord tree is very non-linear with no clear single axis defining the tree in line with multiple random variable specifications. The Discord Chords show groupings in-line with coded parameters where for instance Chords 2 and 3 are both derived from a random Chord 1 at the bottom of the tree.

Figure 3. Average results of Harmony and Discord trials at time series break $t=21$ (Discord21) and at time series break $t=35$ (Discord35) with Distance Unusualness (DU) signal (y-axis) trials over time t (x-axis). The Harmony series shows stable tree distances whereas Discord trials show jumps in tree distance changes that coincide with the encoded regime-shifts. Note that some predictive capability of DU is implied under this algebraic formulation where the signal rises in anticipation of the known break points, but this is related to the smoothing effect where the average of the observations contributes to early rises in the unusualness time series.

Figure 4. Ξ Signal on Left Hand Side (LHS) over each known full-sample financial market regime-shift event: Taper Tantrum (Top Left), COVID-19 Pandemic (Top Right), Inflation Shock (Bottom) set against S&P500 returns on Rights Hand Side (RHS).

Figure 5. S&P500 returns over standard errors before-and-after comparisons between known break date and ε signal date time series splits.

Figure 6. Ξ Signal on Left Hand Side (LHS) for each sample financial market regime-shift event using only data before known break event date: Taper Tantrum (Top Left), COVID-19 Pandemic (Top Right), Inflation Shock (Bottom) set against S&P500 returns on Rights Hand Side (RHS).

Figure 7. S&P500 returns over standard errors before-and-after comparisons between known break date and Ξ signal date time series splits using only before known-break data.

Figure 8. Phylogenetic tree output before (Left) and after (Right) regime change event (labeled by Variable ID, see Table 1).

Figure 9. Percentage change in principal component explanatory power pre-and-post regime shift.

Figure 10. Russian ruble against US dollar (RUBUSD) returns following a \mathcal{E} signal generated using pre-Ukraine invasion data.

Figure 11. Phylogenetic tree output before (Left) and after (Right) out of sample 2022 Ukraine invasion regime change event (labeled by Variable Short ID, see Table 1). Russian ruble variable highlighted.

Figure 12. Ξ Signal on Left Hand Side (LHS) and applied S&P 500 long-short portfolios on Right Hand Side (RHS) based on Ξ Signal extremity thresholds. Portfolios model, with transaction and slippage costs, long S&P 500 during non-signal periods and short during signal periods.

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